

ISic3647

I.Sicily inscription 3647

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

quarzarenite

(di Mistretta)

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Amestratus

Place of origin (modern)

Mistretta

Provenance

Chiesa S. Biagio, Mistretta

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mistretta, Museo Civico
Polivalente, inventory 69/45

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

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